

Hindsight

Graduate History Journal

Spring 2008

Volume II

Hindsight

Graduate History Journal

Hindsight Graduate History Journal is published annually by the graduate students of the Department of History at California State University, Fresno. All interpretations of fact or opinion, as well as content accuracy, are the sole responsibility of the authors and may not reflect the views of the editorial staff.

The journal is also published online at www.csufresno.edu/historydept/hindsight.htm

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The Hindsight Graduate History Journal editorial board wishes to thank the College of Social Sciences and the Division of Graduate Studies at California State University, Fresno for providing funding for this project.

California State University, Fresno

**DEVIL-WORSHIP, REGICIDE, AND COMMERCE:
THE PROFESSIONAL NECROMANCER IN LATE MEDIEVAL
ENGLAND**

By

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At the beginning of the fourteenth century, Walter Langton (d. 1321), Bishop of Coventry and Lichfield, was tried for devil-worship, one of many accusations lodged against him in an attempt to ruin his political career. Although found innocent by Pope Boniface VIII (d. 1303) and the archbishop of Canterbury, Langton remained vulnerable to attacks on his character, and continued to fight for several years against those who resented his extensive landholdings and royal influence after his trial.¹ Boniface VIII, who had cleared Langton of the charges, had also come under attack for similar charges by Phillip IV of France who, only a few years later, instigated charges of diabolism, or devil-worship, against the Knights Templar. The accusation of devil-worship, especially in regards to men belonging to the nobility or possessing high ecclesiastical offices, was an effective method in curbing their authority and influence. With the exception of the trial of Alice Kyteler in Ireland (1324), presided over by an English inquisitor trained on the Continent, the few criminal acts of diabolism for which we have evidence were primarily male-oriented transgressions and mostly motivated by financial concerns. Furthermore, it seems that at this time the hiring of professional necromancers—or men reputed to have skills for

Many thanks to Dr. Marie Kelleher, Dr. Elaine Wida, Dr. Moshe Sluhovsky, Dr. Miguel Aparicio, Samantha Sagui, the participants of the 2007 Medievalism Transformed conference at the University of Wales, Bangor, and my anonymous reviewers at California State University, Fresno for their invaluable comments and suggestions for this article.

¹ The trial of Walter Langton is discussed in depth by Alice Bearwood in her monograph, *The Trial of Walter Langton, Bishop of Lichfield, 1307-1312*, found in *Transactions of the American Philosophical Society* 53 (1964): 1-45.

performing sorcery, usually in the form of diabolical magic—was an activity that was perceived to be potentially useful and personally beneficial. As we shall see below, both the client and the necromancer stood to benefit from their relationship.

Sorcery accusations lodged against members of the English aristocracy, prominent ecclesiastics, and clergymen during this period perhaps resulted from broader changes to the fabric of religious, political, and social life in Europe: the papal schism early in the fourteenth century divided Europe's loyalties, and the papacy would never again wield the influence it once had. In addition, a series of plagues wiped out approximately one-third of Europe's population and, with the lack of able workers to till the land, the binary foundations of most medieval communities—peasants and their lords—began to give way toward more diverse social and economic relationships.² With the onset of uncertain times and the upheaval of traditional social structures, rising concerns about diabolical heresy and illicit magical practices coincided with new religious movements condemned by Christian orthodoxy. Moreover, the ruling and religious elite were not entirely immune to damaging accusations of necromancy and sorcery.

Yet one cannot attribute the seeming rise of sorcery accusations solely to broader social changes in this period, as these social, political, and economic developments do not adequately account for the variations in detail and motivation among different sorcery cases. Instead, one must also look at the world of medieval politics—and the noblemen, aristocratic women, bishops, and kings who inhabited this world—as an exclusive community operating on a similar set of fears, ambitions, and motivations as their less fortunate counterparts. The threat of sorcery was very real to late medieval aristocrats and ecclesiastics, and the purposes of accusing another prominent figure of sorcery did not differ drastically from those of commoners litigating against their neighbors for crimes of the same

² Samuel K. Cohn, *Lust for Liberty: The Politics of Social Revolt in Medieval Europe, 1200-1425* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2006), is a good survey of the effects of economic upheavals and the Black Plague on the population of late medieval Europe.

nature: the accuser not only was able to ruin his opponents by imputing to them occult crimes that could possibly bar them from the political scene, but also could plausibly make such accusations in a culture that supported and spread beliefs about sorcery and cults of devil-worship.

Criminal charges of sorcery directed at clergy and the ruling nobility also appear to have been colored by the necromantic and heretical practices tried at that time in both royal and ecclesiastical courts. As we shall see in the following pages, professional necromancers, or sorcerers who were either paid by, or in the service of, wealthy and influential people, were almost always men. Indeed, wealthy clients, such as noblemen or women, possessed the financial resources and connections necessary to purchase the services of professional necromancers to achieve their malicious ends. Richard Kieckhefer, in his various works on medieval magic and necromancy in the Middle Ages, has discussed evidence such as necromancers' handbooks and inquisitional records for what he perceived to be an all-male clerical underworld, which was inhabited by necromancers with at least some type of religious training.³ It is perhaps no wonder that these professional necromancers—who were almost always drawn from the educated and privileged sectors of society—were sought out by those able to buy their services for personal and political issues needing satisfactory resolutions.

The Business of Magic and Devil-Worship

While the ruling elite's practice of hiring professional necromancers is the best documented, they were not the only ones to engage in this practice; poor commoners and women, too, seem to have widely participated in it. For example, a fifteenth-century case

³ Richard Kieckhefer, "The Holy and the Unholy: Sainthood, Witchcraft, and Magic in Late Medieval Europe." *Journal of Medieval and Renaissance Studies* 23 (1994): 355-85. Arguably, Richard Kieckhefer is one of the foremost authorities on the practice of magic in the medieval world. His books *Magic in the Middle Ages* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989) and especially *Forbidden Rites: A Necromancer's Manual of the Fifteenth Century* (University Park: Pennsylvania State University Press, 1997) discuss in even more detail the taxonomy of magic and the social and intellectual background of necromancy, as well as its prosecution in the courts.

brought before the Chancery dealt with an adulteress named Tanglost, who was accused of hiring two experienced sorceresses to avenge herself on her lover Thomas, who had spurned her after he made an oath that he would refrain from committing adultery.⁴ Tanglost was also said to have killed Thomas's wife with "wychecraft," although this was not the primary charge against her; it was also alleged that Tanglost and two other women fashioned three wax effigies to destroy Thomas. They were thwarted in their efforts when Thomas came to learn about their malicious plans, and Tanglost was forced to flee. Similarly, in a 1446 case brought before a church court in Durham, two women, Mariot de Belton and Isabella Brome, were accused of performing love magic on behalf of single women in want of a husband. They both denied the accusation and were ordered to clear themselves of the charges by compurgation, or by calling upon witnesses able to testify to their good characters.⁵

Of course, it is entirely plausible that women could have hired the services of the local sorceress as well as men, but both the Tanglost and Belton-Brome accounts fail to mention whether any money changed hands. This is not to say that sorceresses-for-hire worked for free or did not engage in some trading of goods, but that women may not have been hired in the same way that their male counterparts were for similar services. In accounts where male sorcerers are involved, there is usually a clear indication as to how they were hired, or how their clients had the means to afford such services. In some of the cases that will be discussed below, the accused necromancers either were motivated by the promise of financial reward or worked under the auspices of generous benefactors or

⁴ C. Trice Martin, "Clerical Life in the Fifteenth Century, as Illustrated by Proceedings of the Court of Chancery," *Archaeologia, or, Miscellaneous Tracts Relating to Antiquity* (1907): 374-5. The ecclesiastical court records in Latin may refer to a woman accused of witchcraft as a *sortilega*, or a sorceress, and sometimes as an *incantatrix*, or an enchantress. However, the secular accounts recorded in English use the terms *witch* and *witchcraft*, often with different spellings, as is the case here with Tanglost.

⁵ James Raine, ed., *Depositions and Other Ecclesiastical Proceedings from the Courts of Durham, Extending from 1311 to the Reign of Elizabeth* (London: J.B. Nichols and Son, 1845), 29: "Mariot de Belton, Isabella Brome. Quod est sortilega, et quod utitur illa arte, et dicit mulieribus solutis, nubere volentibus, quod faciat eas habere quos affectant et desiderant habere. Negat, et habet ad purgandum se cum xij manu. Similiter imponitur Isabellæ. Negat, et habet ad purgandum cum iiii manu."

benefactresses.⁶ For example, the case of Richard Laukiston, which came to the attention of the London Commissary in 1492 on the strength of public rumor, illustrates how a professional sorcerer could have come into contact with a potential client.⁷ Laukiston is accused of having offered to find Margaret Geffrey, a widow whom he attempted to defraud, a rich husband by having a sorcerer perform love magic to entice into marriage a man of her choosing. Laukiston had probably approached Margaret about his offer because he was under the impression that she might have been receptive to his idea, so much so that she would have given up her valuables to pay for such a service. He was proven right, as she did indeed give up two expensive mazers worth 5 marks and 10 shillings.⁸ Margaret was by no means wealthy herself, but she had some financial assets that made the matter of Laukiston's offer plausible in the eyes of the court. Laukiston's offer to make the arrangements with the sorcerer to secure Margaret an advantageous match sheds some light on how professional sorcerers came to be known and recommended: most seem to have been successful at networking. Laukiston's wife knew the sorcerer, who in turn told Laukiston of his cunning skill, who was then recommended to Margaret, and so on and so forth.

⁶ The outsourcing of this type of activity to experienced sorcerers indicates how the economic changes in the fourteenth century that saw the rise in the use of cash capital enabled some to cultivate this "profession" on the side. The epidemic of 1348-9 signaled an upward trend in workers able to take on short-term work for higher wages, and combined with employers tempting their workers to stay by offering extra gratuities in cash, produced a class of consumers with perhaps more disposable income than was the case in the pre-plague years. See Christopher Dyer, *Everyday Life in Medieval England* (London: Hambledon, 1994), 185-6. However, this is a gross oversimplification of the financial situation of the medieval worker in England. Particularly helpful is chapter nine, in which Dyer explains at length the complex financial situation faced by the average worker in medieval England.

⁷ William Hale, ed., *A Series of Precedents and Proceedings in Criminal Causes: Extending from the Year 1475 to 1640* (London: F. & J. Rivington, 1847), 32-3, has the entire trial transcribed in original Latin and in the vernacular English of the defendants.

⁸ *Ibid.*; "...Ricardus protulit ista verba vel eis consimilia, predicte Margarete in Anglicis, Thow arte a poor widow, and it wer almes to helpe the to a mariage, and if thow wilt do any cost in spendyng any money, thow shalt have a man worth a thousand pounds. Tunc respondebat predicta Margareta vidua, How may that be? Tunc dixit Laukiston, My wif knoweth a connyng man, that by his connyng can cause a woman to have any man that she hath favour to, and that shalbe upon warranties; for she hath put it in execucion afore tyme, and this shall cost money. Tunc dixit predicta Margareta, I have no good save ii masers for to fynde me, my moder, and my children, and if thei wer sold and I faile of my purpose, I, my moder, and my children wer undoen. Tunc dixit dictus Ricardus Laukiston, Delyver me the masers, and I wille warrant thyn entente shalbe fulfilled. Tunc predicta Margareta deliberavit sibi ii murras ad valorem v marcarum et xs. in pecuneis."

The centrality of networks and word-of-mouth in the linking of necromancer and client can also be seen in a 1331 Southwark case adjudicated at King's Bench. Three men—Andrew of Oxford, John son of Robert of Gloucester, and Robert de la Marche—appeared at court for conspiring to kill a man named Robert of Ely and his mother Margery by having Marche perform a specialized type of sorcery. Andrew had heard about Marche's talent for alchemy and magic and recommended him to John, who had apparently implored and paid Marche a good amount of money to perform some complicated magical procedures that included the use of spells and image magic.⁹ The apparent availability of many of these professional necromancers, who were offering their services to those able to afford them (and especially in relatively densely-populated areas such as London), indicates that there was likely a high demand for their services. Indeed, in 1426, a knight and a yeoman, along with a number of their associates, were accused in London for contracting the services of *multiple* expert necromancers, one of whom was a chaplain, to “weaken and annihilate, subtly consume and altogether destroy” a certain William Botreaux by engaging in “soothsaying, necromancy and art magic.”¹⁰ The demand for professional necromancers for homicidal magic, especially in relation to premeditated plans for murder, was likely a “specialty” for which potential clients especially valued the necromancer's occult skills.

However, not all necromancers were hired in the sense that they were promised remuneration for their services. In cases dealing with necromancers and the nobility, the relationship between the two is best characterized as a form of patronage. Indeed, the patron-necromancer relationship is colorfully illustrated in the 1330 confession of Edmund, the Earl of Kent (1301-1330), which he gave to the Coroner of the King's House.¹¹ In the

⁹ G.O. Sayles, ed., *Select Cases in the Court of King's Bench under Edward III*, vol. V (London: Selden Society, 1958), 53-7.

¹⁰ *Calendar of the Patent Rolls, Preserved in the Public Record Office, Henry VI A.D. 1422-1429* (Nendeln/Liechtenstein: Kraus Reprint, 1971), 363.

¹¹ The transcript of the Earl of Kent's confession can be found in the *Journal of the British Archaeological Association* VII (1851): 140-3.

confession, he described how he contracted the services of a certain friar to summon a devil in order to ascertain whether his brother, King Edward II (r. 1307-1327), was still living. Edmund was executed on political grounds for conspiring to put the deceased Edward II, who he was led to believe was still alive, back on the throne. Edmund's removal from the political scene ensured that the interests of the dowager Queen Isabella and her associates were protected, as they had wanted the weak Edward II removed from power. But why was it necessary to accuse the Earl of Kent of diabolical improprieties in particular? The account of his confession indicated that there were some incriminating letters of dubious origins that nonetheless, in the hands of Queen Isabella, were able to secure Edmund's conviction for high treason.¹² One can deduce from the document that Edmund's demands to the reprobate friar, who had "raysed up a devell" for him and engaged in blatant apostasy, were meant to convey to the English people and Parliament that the popular Earl of Kent was not only a traitor but a heretical one at that.¹³ The idea that noblemen or high churchmen, such as Walter Langton, the aforementioned Bishop of Coventry and Lichfield, and Edmund, the Earl of Kent, consorted with the devil or demons, might have been easily believed in a society where the belief in sorcery was prevalent. These men were in positions of authority and were seen as able to secure the services of demons or those who knew how to summon them.

The frequency with which magic and diabolism were conflated made it problematic, even for educated churchmen, to discern the distinctions between the two. If a pact was made with the devil, the human supplicant was allegedly given supernatural powers in exchange for his or her loyalty and soul. Hence, sorcery and devil-worship were one and the same to theologians and inquisitors who wrote about magic and witchcraft during the late

¹² Ibid., 142.

¹³ Ibid., 140.

medieval period.¹⁴ According to their perspective, a pact with the devil or a demon served a purpose similar to the hiring of a professional necromancer: the devil or demon was in fact “commissioned” by the sorcerer to either do his bidding or imbue him with the powers necessary to bring about the desired results. The relationship between the demonic force and the sorcerer is thrown into sharp relief in a curious 1337 case from a manorial court in Hatfield. One man was tried for failing to deliver the devil to another man in a commercial transaction, perhaps indicating how ideas about devil-worship and sorcery were incorporated into the broader commercial culture of late medieval England:

Robert de Roderham appeared against John de Ithen, because he had not kept the agreement made between them, and therefore complains that on a certain day and year, at Thorne, there was an agreement between the aforementioned Robert and John whereby the said John sold to the said Robert the devil, bound in a certain bond, for three pence halfpenny...[Yet] the said John refused to deliver the said devil...to the great detriment of the said Robert...and because it appeared to the court that such a suit ought not to exist among Christians, the aforementioned parties are therefore adjourned, as far as hell for the hearing of their judgments...¹⁵

Although it is most likely that this “case” was in fact an attempt at injecting some levity into a hypothetical case for students studying contract law, the details are nevertheless suggestive of a male-centric view of how the power relationship between the demon and the male sorcerer favored the latter, with the demon having severely limited powers in relation to its human master. The power of the devil and the devil’s supernatural hold over his human subjects is amusingly diminished here, as it seems that the devil was merely an object

¹⁴ Michael D. Bailey, “The Feminization of Magic and the Emerging Idea of the Female Witch in the Late Middle Ages,” *Essays in Medieval Studies* 19 (2002): 120-134, has a good summary of this argument.

¹⁵ Thomas Blount, “Conventio,” *Nomo-Lexicon: A Law Dictionary* (Los Angeles: Sherwin & Freutel, 1970): “Robertus de Roderham obtulit se versus Johannem de Ithen de eo quod non teneat Conventionem inter eos factam, & unde queritur, quod certo die & anno apud Thorne convenit inter prædictum Robertum & Johannem, quod prædictus Johannes vendidit prædicto Roberto Diabolum ligatum in quodam ligamine pro iii^d. ob...idem Johannes prædictum Diabolum deliberare noluit...ad grave dampnum ipsum Roberti...Et quia videtur Curia quod tale placitum non jacet inter Christianos, Ideo partes prædicti adjournantur usque in infernum, ad audiendum iudicium suum...” Cf. C. L’Estrange Ewen, *Witchcraft and Demonism* (London: Heath Cranton, 1933), 33-4. Ewen does not seem to question whether this trial indeed took place, despite its ridiculousness. He barely analyzes it, which suggests that he was merely interested in the account as an anomalous oddity that had to be included for the sake of making his exhaustive work seem more complete.

that could be bartered, traded, or bought under ordinary and mundane circumstances, and acquired in such a way because it was believed to be a relatively inexpensive and useful object for someone to have. The two men in this account are clearly in a position of authority over the diabolical force, since they have the power to dispose of the devil in any which way they choose. This, we might note, contrasts starkly with some of the accounts from the Continent that describe women being decidedly subordinate to their demonic familiars. Indeed, in Ireland, the near-contemporary account of the trial of Alice Kyteler, tried according to Continental ideas about witches, describes how she and a coven of female devotees paid homage and made sacrifices to the devil.¹⁶ Alice herself was accused of sexually submitting to her demonic familiar, who took on various shapes and disguises.

However, even if we regard the Hatfield case as a sort of quodlibetal exercise, or perhaps a theological joke, written for the sake of law students in need of a little amusement, it still reveals how the author of the account viewed the role of the devil in human affairs. By describing the overly ridiculous situation of the devil as being some sort of desired commodity that could be bought and sold at will, the author throws into sharp relief how diabolical nuisances often tempted the weak and the corruptible. More importantly, the exaggerated absurdity of the idea that the devil could trade hands so easily is meant to highlight what so many thought was the frightening nature of devil-worship: the devil's services could indeed be bought, but not for a pittance. It would cost one's immortal soul, ensuring eternal damnation.

Sorcery cases involving diabolical necromancy, once brought to secular and ecclesiastical justices, could not have escaped the notice of prominent royal figures or churchmen who wished to prosecute necromancers more fervently. One such case from Southwark in 1371 describes a certain man named John Crok, who was tried by a royal court

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L.S. Davidson and J.O. Ward, eds., *The Sorcery Trial of Alice Kyteler: A Contemporary Account Together with Related Documents in English Translation* (Binghamton: Center for Medieval and Early Renaissance Studies, State University of New York at Binghamton, 1993).

for invocation and using a Saracen's skull, which he had bought in Toledo, and a necromancer's manual found in his bag in order to trap a demonic spirit "so that the said spirit would answer questions."¹⁷ Crok was dismissed after having sworn an oath that he would refrain in the future from engaging in such practices, and the bag holding all the items was destroyed by the bailiff; yet this case apparently came to the attention of the king, who directed the archbishop of Canterbury's bailiff to immediately take action against Crok and to deal with the matter of the Saracen's skull, having found the situation sufficiently disturbing.¹⁸ While the primary charge against Crok was for the invocation of a demonic force, the justices seemed to have been more preoccupied by the forbidden items purchased abroad, without which Crok's attempts at magic would have failed. Clearly, the success of this type of diabolical magic hinged on the sorcerer's wherewithal to purchase the devices necessary to harness the demon's powers.

The few legal and narrative references to diabolism that survive in England at this time indicate that the notion of devil-worship was widespread across all levels of medieval society, but that the intentions behind the summoning of diabolical forces were relatively benign and somewhat materialistic, and not used—just to provide an example—to smite neighbors with sickness or death, as we see in witchcraft trials of early modern England. One such account in a 1366 chronicle reveals how financial considerations played into the practice of diabolism. It tells a story of a man who confessed to his neighbors that he had made a pact with the devil to overshadow his competitors in the carpentry business:

In this year a certain carpenter died, who, over the past fifteen years, worshipped the devil, so that he could excel in his craft over the other carpenters. Having foreknowledge of his end, he asked his comrades that they not permit him to harm anyone around him. But with all of them having been summoned, they returned, placing him in an empty room so that he might get some sleep. Shortly after waking to

¹⁷ Sayles, *Select Cases in the Court of King's Bench*, vol. VI, 163: "Qui dicit quod capud illud fuit capud cuiusdam Sarisini et quod ipse capud predictum in Tolet in quadam ciuitate in Ispannia emit causa includendi in eo quendam spiritum ut idem spiritus ad interrogata responderet..."

¹⁸ Ibid.

his shouting, upon entering the room they discovered him extracting his own intestines from his stomach; putting back his still warm entrails into his belly, they called together all their neighbors and priests, along with the Bishop, for witness, and when he confessed in secret and openly of his sins he died in the Catholic faith having received the holy viaticum.¹⁹

While no judicial proceedings were recorded, one can conclude from this rather mundane account of devil-worship that the man was chiefly motivated by financial gain. The chronicler's moral angle to this story makes it clear to the readers that the carpenter ultimately caused his own physical deterioration by compromising his spiritual allegiance to the faith. It is interesting to note that the carpenter's neighbors seemed to have known about his pact with the devil and that he still had friends who rallied for his well-being and redemption. Perhaps the man's devil-worship was not seen by his neighbors and associates as too horrible, since he was not specifically targeting anyone with malicious magic. The evidence suggests that, at least during the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries in England, demonic pacts were at the very least a small part of a popular conception of what sorcery could involve, but that diabolical practices were aimed toward resolving personal or financial problems rather than bringing physical harm to others. The prevalence of women as targets of accusations involving the diabolical pact in early modern England was perhaps indicative of the shift in the perception of witchcraft as being a primarily female crime. What exactly precipitated a change in the gendering of diabolical magic is difficult to say, but perhaps the gradual spread of ideas about devil-worship eventually influenced the ways in which women were seen to obtain the powers needed to make their witchcraft effective.

Diabolical magic at this time was also intimately associated with the business of magic and sorcery, which often included the exchange of money or favors for the performance of a

¹⁹ James Tait, ed., *Chronica Johannis de Reading et anonymi Cantuariensis, 1346-1367* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1914), 176: "Obiit et hoc anno quidam artifex lignarius qui annis quindecim præteritis diabolo servivit, ut ceteros carpentarios excelleret operando. Ille finis sui præcius a sociis petiit, ne aliquid quod posset lædere alicui circa se permitterent. At illum, sublatis omnibus, in camera vacua collocantes ut sompnum caperet, redierunt; clamore cujus paulo post excitati, cameram ingredienti propria viscera de ventre extrahentem reperierunt; quæ adhuc calida in utero reponentes, vicinos in testimonium sacerdotisque cum Corpore Dominico convocarunt, ac ubi secreta et palam de peccatis confessus cum sacro viatico in fide Catholica decessit."

certain act of sorcery. As we have learned, the sorcerer-for-hire was used by noble and commoner alike for very specific, and usually very personal, reasons. The evident demand for the services of professional sorcerers suggests that a good number of men, and maybe even some women, made at least a partial living this way, and that there was never really a shortage of people in need of such services. The specialized skills of a necromancer-for-hire were deemed necessary for the proper performance of serious types of magic, such as homicidal magic, that could potentially alter one's standing within the community. As we shall see below, the far more serious kind of homicidal sorcery—regicidal magic—was also typically performed by professional necromancers, as they were perceived to have the ability to engage in such pernicious sorcery with adequate skill and discretion.

Regicide

Legal and narrative accounts of regicidal magic in late medieval England prominently feature expert necromancers, whose clients were either rich or influential enough to secure their services. Usually, the individuals contributing monetary aid or another form of support to the professional necromancer for regicide were also implicated as part of this larger conspiracy against the king. The 1325 testimony from Robert le Mareschal, who lodged an appeal against Master John of Nottingham and twenty-five burghers from Coventry, describes how he was a boarder at Master John's residence when these twenty-five men beseeched both him and Master John to perform murderous sorcery directed at the Prior of Coventry, a few of his supporters, and the king himself (Edward II).²⁰

Men's predominance in the practice of diabolism or professional necromancy seemed to be intimately tied to their financial circumstances, and this was particularly true when a certain malefactor paid another to perform sorcery, or when the sorcerer had to purchase special items needed to work his sorcery. This connection is well supported by the case of

²⁰ F. Palgrave, ed., *Parliamentary Writs and Writs of Military Summons*, vol. II (London: Record Commission, 1832), 269-70.

Robert and Master John, whose reputation as a necromancer was apparently well-known, since the burghers negotiated a pricey deal with both Master John and Robert: the former would receive twenty pounds and the latter fifteen, and they were duly supplied with the items needed for the task. Master John and Robert fashioned six wax figurines in the likeness of their intended targets, but made a seventh in the image of a certain Richard de Sowe, which they set aside in order that they might test the efficacy of their magic. According to Robert's account, Master John told him to impale the forehead of Richard's image with a lead skewer, then bade him to visit Richard the next day to inspect their handiwork. Richard was apparently in a lot of pain, shrieking, braying, crying out "Harrow!" until Master John stuck the skewer in the heart of the figurine a couple of days later, which then, shortly thereafter, caused Richard's death. Indeed, image magic was a popular form of sorcery requiring easily attainable skills that practically anyone could learn, especially when compared to the more intricate rituals typical to necromantic practices. Master John probably had some knowledge of necromancy, but fused it with perhaps more traditional forms of sympathetic magic using dolls or wax images; furthermore, he was probably perceived to be successful at it, since he developed a reputation as a "nigromauncer" whose services could not be bought on the cheap.²¹

Regicide by way of magic was essentially an anonymous crime of treason; for this reason, it was difficult to prosecute and required the cooperation of those willing to come forward to confess their culpability or inform on other people's regicidal activities. Robert's appeal to the Coroner of the Hospital, and then to the King's Bench, was an attempt to commute his sentence to a lighter one by naming his accomplices in the matter of Richard de Sowe's death, thus forcing this criminal matter to come to light. Master John ended up dying in prison but the other men were acquitted in *visnet*—meaning, by a jury of twelve

²¹ Ibid.

men.²² As this case came to the attention of the King's Bench, it probably reinforced among the ruling elite the terrible image of the male sorcerer who, at will, *and secretly*, was able to cause death or ruin to the king, important churchmen, and magistrates.

Since sorcery could be performed secretly for malicious purposes and political advancement, prominent women of the royal court were not above being blamed for using magic or employing necromancers to carry out their regicidal conspiracies. Having magic performed on their behalf illuminates one of the ways in which these women were able to exercise agency behind the scenes in the male-dominated world of high politics; their roles in these alleged plots tended to highlight how their male contemporaries viewed their power or influence on the politics of the court. To take one notable example, Alice Perrers (d. 1400), mistress of King Edward III (r. 1327-1377), was accused of having hired a Dominican friar, who at first claimed to be a physician, to perform love magic directed at the king.²³ According to the chronicle, written by a monk at St. Albans, the Dominican forged two wax effigies in the likeness of Alice and Edward, and utilizing these with some potent herbs, managed to get the king under Alice's thrall. The author also makes a curious reference to a *magus famosissimus*, the ancient Egyptian King Nectanebo, and the making of memory rings so that the king could not forget his mistress.²⁴ The monk's allusions to ancient magic may illuminate his belief in the potency of the Dominican's sorcery, as he provides the mystical precedents for the practice of this type of magic. The sorcerer-monk of these tales is likely a negative projection of the piously humble monk, whose inverted image of malice and worldliness enhanced the spiritual piety of the true mendicant.

²² Ibid.; see also William Renwick Riddell, "A Trial for Witchcraft Six Hundred Years Ago," *Journal of the American Institute of Criminal Law and Criminology* 8 (1917): 40-44, for his useful explanation of the legal jargon found in the text.

²³ Edward Maunde Thompson, ed., *Chronicon Angliae, ab anno domini 1328 usque ad annum 1388* (London: Longman, 1874), 97-100.

²⁴ Ibid., 98; George Lyman Kittredge, *Witchcraft in Old and New England* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1929), 105. As legend has it, the exiled Nectanebo II came to Phillip of Macedon's court in the guise of a magician. He seduced Olympias, Phillip's wife, and from their coupling Alexander the Great was conceived.

The regicide case made against Joan of Navarre (1370-1437), dowager queen and stepmother of Henry V (r. 1413-1422), had aspects similar to the Perrers case, although it was the king himself who accused her of encouraging her sometime confessor Friar Randolf to engage in regicidal magic. It was announced in Parliament that "Queen Joan of England had schemed and imagined the death and destruction of our Lord the King in the most horrible manner that one could devise."²⁵ A contemporary narrative source is much clearer on the subject of the alleged magical harm directed at the king: it states that Friar Randolf had specifically used "sorcerye" and "nigromancie" when he had later confessed to his crimes.²⁶

However, the consequences of Queen Joan's alleged crimes were not altogether dire. Her lands were conveniently forfeited to the crown in 1420 following this incident, and she was put under house arrest while her accomplice was incarcerated. Despite all this, Queen Joan was kept relatively well during her years without her dower lands; the king paid the salaries of the men under her employ and apparently kept her household well supplied with food, livestock, and other myriad items necessary for her retinue.²⁷ In fact, in the same year before his death in September of 1422, Henry sent out a writ expressing his will that his stepmother should be restored to her dower. The queen then petitioned to Parliament on this matter, and she was then monetarily compensated for the loss of her lands.²⁸

The reasons for Henry's personal vendetta against Queen Joan, and why it took such an ugly turn, are unknown, but it can be said with some certainty that Henry and his prelates were paranoid about the presence of sorcerers in the realm. In fact, the king's fear is further illuminated by a 1419 mandate to the bishop of London, in which the archbishop of

²⁵ *Rotuli parliamentorum; ut et petitiones, et placita in parlamento*, vol. IV (London: 1767-83), 118. "...Johane Roigne d'Engleterre, avoit compassez & ymaginez la mort & destruction de n[ot]r[r]e dit S[ic] le Roi, en le plus haute & horrible manere, q[ue] l'en purroit deviser."

²⁶ Nicholas Harris Nicolas, ed., *A Chronicle of London, from 1089 to 1483* (London: Longman, 1827), 107-8.

²⁷ *Calendar of the Patent Rolls, Henry V A.D. 1416-1422*, vol. II (Nendeln/Liechtenstein: Kraus Reprint, 1971), 276, 294, 304, 362, 396, 402.

²⁸ *Rotuli parliamentorum*, 247-9; *Calendar of the Patent Rolls, Henry VI A.D. 1422-1429*, 84, 166.

Canterbury describes ordering processions and prayers on behalf of the king in his war against the French.²⁹ Above all, the king desired protection from the “superstitious operations of necromancers, particularly like those that recently had been plotted through some against his person, according to reports.”³⁰ Because so much of Henry’s power as king depended on his ability to be successful in war, the idea that a sorcerer’s pernicious magic could tip the scales against Henry’s army—even if only in one battle—was a terrifying thought indeed.

That a network of sorcerers was behind intricate and perfidious plots involving regicide or some type of treachery directed at the royal household may not have been merely a figment of a monarch’s wild imagination. A monk at St. Alban’s told of an incident that took place in 1430, when “around Christmastime certain witches, seven of them from different parts of the realm, were captured in London and incarcerated at Fleet Prison, all of whom plotted the death of the king.”³¹ The text is frustratingly vague on the details, but the monk suggests that this was a coven of female witches (*maleficae*) who, although individually hailing from different parts of the country, convened in London in order to collude more efficiently with each other. The notion that these women, when united in their wickedness, possessed the type of agency that could possibly bring about the demise of a king shows how learned conceptions of sorcery envisioned women as being part of this bigger picture. Women could exact the same results as the monk-necromancers described in the aforementioned accounts, but did not utilize the same learned methods.

As was seen in the aforementioned accusations involving women of the royal court and their personal magicians, the employment of male necromancers to perform sorcery for

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David Wilkins, ed., *Concilia magna Britanniae et Hiberniae*, vol. III (London: Fleetstreet, 1727), 393-4.

³⁰

Ibid., 393. “...superstitutionis necromanticorum operationibus, talibus praesertim, quales jam tarde in perniciem et destructionem personae suae per nonnullos, ut refertur, excogitatae fuerant.”

³¹

John Amundesham, *Annales monasterii S. Albani*, ed. Thomas Riley, vol. I (Nendeln/Liechtenstein: Kraus Reprint, 1965), 56-7. “Circa hos dies Christi Natalitios, quaedam maleficae, numero septem, de diversis partibus regni, captae sunt in Londiniis, et incarcerantur apud le Fleete, quae machinatae sunt interitum Regis.”

them is indicative not only of personal and political issues these ladies sought to resolve via magic, but also of the lengths to which they would use their wealth and influence.

According to several fifteenth-century accounts, one noblewoman, Eleanor Cobham, Duchess of Gloucester, attempted to use her position of power and connections to kill the king by way of a certain Roger Bolingbroke's "werchyng of sorcery."³² She was accused in 1441 of conspiring with Bolingbroke, who was a clerk, Canon Thomas Southwell, and the infamous Margery Jourdemayn, for attempted regicide.

While this could be classified strictly as a case of attempted regicide—and Bolingbroke indeed was hanged, drawn, and quartered like all common traitors—the case involved other elements of interest relevant to a discussion of sorcery practice among the ruling elite, such as Eleanor's recruitment of various sorcerers, all of whom had different positions within their lay and ecclesiastical communities. When Bolingbroke was arraigned for the charges brought against him, he was made to stand on the scaffold with all of his "instrumentis" around him. He was then examined and eventually convicted before the lords of the king's council—his benefit of clergy apparently not being enough of a reason to save him from secular justice and the scaffold. Canon Southwell died in prison, for his role in the matter, which was apparently to say masses consecrating Bolingbroke's instruments of "nygromancie," which were images of either the devil or the king, made of silver, wax, or other metals.³³ Eleanor acknowledged using these items, but she claimed to have wanted these diabolical items to help her bear a child "by hir lord, the Duke of Gloucestre," meaning that she had hired Bolingbroke for that purpose.³⁴ Eleanor's fertility problems were probably very serious, as she also consulted with the notorious Margery, who was

³² Nicolas, 128.

³³ William Marx and John Silvester Davies, eds., *An English Chronicle, 1377-1461* (Rochester: Boydell Press, 2003), 76, 147-8, 151.

³⁴ Friederich W. D. Brie, ed., *The Brut; or, The Chronicles of England*, vol. II (New York: Kraus Reprint, 1971), 480; Thomas Hearne, ed., *Liber niger scaccarii*, vol. II (Oxonii: e Theatro Sheldoniano, 1728), 460-1; Marx and Davies, 93. The story's appearance in at least three different chronicles may point to either its popularity amongst the neighboring communities or the importance which the authors attributed to it.

known to her community as the Witch of Eye (meaning, the Eye manor near the city of Westminster). Nine years earlier Margery was apprehended for sorcery (along with a monk and a clerk), but was released from prison when her husband paid a bond to the Chancery.³⁵ However, this time, Margery did not get off so easily: she was burned at Smithfield, probably as a relapsed heretic. The Duchess herself was given penance in the form of public humiliation; she was ordered to walk through the streets “openly berhede with a keverchef on hir hede” and with a penitential taper in her hand to various places.³⁶ Then she was sentenced to life in prison for the charges imputed to her.

As the above examples illustrate, aristocratic women such as the Duchess of Gloucester and the dowager Queen Joan were perceived to have resources and people available to them for the implementation of their malevolent plans. Ecclesiastics, too, were considered particularly dangerous. As is made clear in the example below, ecclesiastics’ international connections were thought by many to afford them greater means for magical devilry. In London in 1496, a Frenchman, Bernard de Vignolles, confessed in a deposition given to the king that he was the agent of John Kendal, the prior of St. John of Rhodes, a knight (Kendal’s nephew), and the archdeacon of London, all of whom had hatched a plot to murder the royal family and some of Henry VII’s councilors by using sorcery.³⁷ Bernard had been ordered by Kendal and the archdeacon to meet up with a Spanish astrologer in Rome to acquire a certain magical ointment to smear across a doorway entrance so that when the king passed through it those who loved him most would be compelled to rise up and kill him.³⁸ Bernard, on his way back to England, was not able to go through with the

³⁵ Thomas Rymer, ed., *Fœdera, conventiones, literæ, et cujuscunque generis acta publica, inter reges Angliæ*, 3d ed. (Farnborough: Gregg P., 1967), 178: “...dicta Margeria exoneretur de Prisonsa, sub Securitate Mariti sui in Cancellaria Regis facienda.”

³⁶ Nicolas, 129.

³⁷ The text of the deposition can be found in James Gairdner, ed., *Letters and Papers Illustrative of the Reigns of Richard III and Henry VII* (Nendeln/Liechtenstein: Kraus Reprint, 1965), 318-23.

³⁸ *Ibid.*, 320: “...oingnement, qui estoit en ladite boueste, au longe et travers de quelque huys ou porte par ou passeroit le roy, affin que passat par dessus; le quel astrologe disoit, que sil est ainsi fait, que ceulx qui avoient et portoint plus damour au roy, que seroient ceulx qui turoint le roy.”

plan and decided to throw away the box containing the magical ointment. He instead bought a similar box from an *apoticaire* and filled it with foul-smelling substances to make it seem like the original, and brought this ersatz potion back to the conspirators. Kendal was not able to go through with the plot either, and told Bernard to get rid of the box. Since, obviously, there was no murder and hence no crime, it never went beyond Bernard's confession, and the king gave Kendal a general pardon that same year.³⁹

Regicide was a treasonous crime punishable by death, and with the perceived increase in the amount of necromancers and witches in the realm, it also seemed increasingly urgent to prosecute these malefactors, whose treachery and vice would be practically impossible to trace because of the anonymity that sorcery practices provided. Bernard's testimony implicated prominent church figures in this regicidal conspiracy, but most importantly, he was able to put a face on a generally faceless crime. But if this story tells us anything, it is that those accused of working sorcery for regicidal purposes, with the exception of the unnamed London witches in the above mentioned chronicle, tended to be easily identifiable people with vested interests in the Crown or the Church. The same could also be said of the accusers, whose status or security was better guarded by the removal of threatening individuals from the political arena. The Robert le Mareschal case was an example of an attempt at regicide that was prompted by purely monetary concerns, although the burghers that provided the funding were unequivocal about their treasonous wishes.

Since men, especially clergymen, were also by and large more educated than women, it was they who were perceived to have been more likely to cultivate viable professions as necromancers, and more able to entice both commoners and nobility with certain promises about their abilities. Perhaps encouraged to develop such a livelihood by those willing to pay for their services with money or goods, professional necromancers in this sense were not much different from goldsmiths, shoemakers, and other traditionally male-dominated trades

³⁹ *Calendar of the Patent Rolls Henry VII A.D. 1485-1509*, vol. II (Nendeln/Liechtenstein: Kraus Reprint, 1971),

that required a certain amount of training. Of course, this comparison falls short when one considers the guilds that set prices and controlled the standards by which young men became apprenticed, but the evidence shows that necromancers-for-hire had to cultivate a reputation for their experience and skill in sorcery in order for them to be recommended to potential clients—and this probably meant that the professional necromancer must have had, at one point, several satisfied customers.